

Japan-India partnership and opportunities for North-East India

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Abstract: *In today's evolving geopolitical scenario in the Indo-Pacific, Japan –India partnership could turn out to be one of the most mutually productive and lasting one. Japan is set to reorient its foreign policy priorities in the backdrop the changing geopolitical matrix where the eminent rise of China and downturn of its longtime ally US in the region and speculations of the end of the dollar monopoly is the world economics is going around. Japan is in search for a partner which shares its democratic values of democracy and at the same time an economic and strategic partner. Here, India fits the bill. Japan hopes that strengthening strategic and economic partnership with India is in its best interest for now and for times to come. Japan is under pressure from the US to pay for the expenses in exchange of security it offers to Japan. In this connection Japan has decided that instead of paying to USA military force to guard their country, Japan should use their resources to bolster their own defence capabilities. For this to happen Japan needs to strengthen its allies in Asia to deal with Chinese military expansion. Here the significance of east and Northeastern part of India comes to the picture in Japanese scheme of things. Japan's interest in India's Northeast arises from overlapping strategic, economic, infrastructural and geopolitical calculations. Japan treats the region as a gateway to connecting Japan with South Asia and Southeast Asia while balancing China's rise, securing supply chains and expanding economic opportunities.*

Keywords: *Japan, India, North East India, strategic, connectivity, economic corridor*

Introduction

Japan-India relations date back sixth century B.C. when Buddhism was introduced to Japan. Buddhism was the medium through which Indian culture was transferred to Japan and impacted Japanese culture, and this had a great impact on Japanese people's sense of closeness to India. Some of the Seven Lucky Gods of the Japanese mythology also collectively known as Shichifukujin have their roots in Hindu traditions.¹ After World War II, India did not attend the San Francisco Conference as India considers the treaty to be discriminatory for Japan but decided to conclude a separate Peace Treaty with Japan on 28 April 1952,

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marking the beginning of diplomatic relations between the two nations. This treaty was one of the first peace treaties Japan signed after WWII. The relationships between the two countries grown steadily over the years to cover a wide range of areas of cooperation including political, defense and security, economic, science and technology, education, cultural and people to people exchange. In the post-World War II period, India's iron ore helped a great deal in Japan's recovery from the devastation. India has been the first and largest recipient of Japanese ODA (Official Development Assistance) Loan for the past decades. Delhi Metro is one of the most successful examples of Japanese cooperation through the utilization of ODA. Japan continues to cooperate in supporting strategic connectivity linking South Asia to Southeast Asia through the synergy between "Act East" policy and "Partnership for Quality Infrastructure". Besides Japan and India had committed to build high speed Railway in India by introducing Japan's Shinkansen system, which is the flagship project of Japan-India Relation. (Loan of 276 billion Yen (FY 2024) Grants of 0.2 billion yen (FY 2024), Technical Cooperation of 7 billion Yen (FY 2024)).²

Some of the landmark agreements signed between Japan and India since the beginning of 21st century is:

- 2000- "Global Partnership between Japan and India"
- 2005- Started Japan-India annual summit meetings which are held in respective capitals.
- 2006- India Japan relationship was elevated to the "Global and Strategic Partnership"
- 2014- Upgraded the relationship to "special and Global Partnership".
- 2015- The two countries resolved to transform the Japan India Special strategic and Global Partnership into a deep, broad based and action-oriented partnership, which reflects a broad convergence of their long-term political, economic and strategic goals.
- 2025- "India-Japan Joint Vision for next Decade" released. The two countries announced "Japan and India Vision 2025, special strategic and Global Partnership working together for Peace and Prosperity of the Indo-Pacific region and the World. It is a joint statement that would serve as a guide for the "new era in Japan –India relations. "Free and Open Indo-Pacific" is their commitment.

There is growing synergy between India's Act-East Policy, Indo-Pacific vision based on the principle of SAGAR, and Indo-Pacific Oceans Initiative (IPOI) on the one hand and Japan's Free and Open Indo-Pacific Vision on the other. Japan has also agreed to lead the cooperation on the trade, connectivity and Maritime transport pillar of IPOI. Japan has also joined India led initiatives such as International Solar Alliance (ISA), Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure (CDRI) and Leadership Group for Industry Transition (Lead IT). India and Japan are also cooperating under Japan-Australia-India-US Quad Framework and India-

Japan-Australia Supply Chain Resilience Initiative (SCRI). India Japan Act east Forum was established in December 2017, with the aim to provide a platform for India-Japan collaboration under the rubric of India's Act East policy and Japan's vision of a Free and Open Indo Pacific". The forum identifies specific projects for economic modernization of India's North-East Region such as those pertaining to connectivity, development infrastructure, industrial linkages as well as people to people contacts.³

Japan-India security convergence in post-cold war era

Japan's security policy consists of three pillars-

- 1) Maintaining the Japan-US security arrangements;
- 2) Securing its own defence capability; and
- 3) Making diplomatic efforts to secure stability in international politics.

For Japan, with a minimum self-defence capability, the US deterrence based on the Japan-US security arrangement is essential. Japan considers extensive U.S. Japan cooperative relations anchored by the Japan-US Security arrangements are also instrumental in securing world peace and stability. Japan is of the view that, the US presence in the Asia-Pacific region serves as a stabilizing factor for the region and the Japan-US security arrangements are an indispensable foundation to promote peace and prosperity for the whole Asia-Pacific region. However, under its Peace constitution, Japan has been developing a moderate yet effective defence capability based on the basic principle of maintaining an exclusively defence capability and of not becoming a military power capable of threatening other nations. Admittedly, some Asian countries are concerned that Japan might become a military power. Thus, it is important for Japan to continue explaining its defence policy, including its exclusively defence-oriented policy at every opportunity.

As per the changing security architecture in the immediate aftermath of the end of cold war, the US, the flag bearer of maintaining peace and security in Asia-Pacific region, started shifting the policies towards promoting consolidation, integration and rationalization of military forces. The general reduction for the US forces in the Asia-Pacific region excluding Guam has started since 1990. The first phase of reduction was completed at the end of 1992 by which 25,000 US military personnel have been reduced from the Asia Pacific region.

On the other hand, in the Russian side also, there was a diminishing trend of warship and warplane activities and large-scale military exercises. The number of their ground forces divisions will continue to be cut, and

the withdrawal from Mongolia has been completed by the end of 1990s. In the meantime, for China, under the basic principle of “following the general trend of economic construction”, continues to promote modernization of its defence capabilities as one of its “four modernizations” policy. It has been trying to modernize various armaments in addition to carrying out institutional reforms such as reorganization of military forces resulting in a reduction of army personnel by 1 million after 1985.

There are four particularly important elements for Japan’s effort toward peace and prosperity in the Asia Pacific region. During the cold war and its immediate aftermath–. First, maintenance of the presence and engagement of the United States: second, diplomatic efforts for the solution of conflicts and confrontation: third, promotion of region-wide political and security dialogues: and fourth, promotion of economic development in the region.

Japan considers the presence of the US forces and their engagements are widely recognized as a stabilizing factor not only in military but also political terms. It strongly urged United States to maintain its forward deployment strategy. Japan provides the facilities and areas by the Japanese government based on the Japan-US security arrangements and its payment of expenses of the US forces in Japan (USFJ) from an indispensable basis for this forward deployment.

One significant strategic instrument of Japan for enhancing peace and security in the world is its ODA (Official Development Assistance). It is a government program providing aid (loans, grants, technical help) to developing nations managed largely by Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA). It is a low-interest, long-term funds for infrastructure giving direct aid and training for personnel and also collaborating with private companies for efficient project implementation. Japan provides ODA in accordance with the following principles:

Full attention should be paid to trends in recipient countries’ military expenditures, their development and production of mass destruction weapons and missiles, their exports and imports of arms etc.

Full attention should be paid to efforts for promoting democratization and the introduction of a market-oriented economy, and the situation regarding the securing of basic human rights and freedoms in the recipient country. These principles aim to maintain and promote international peace and stability. They are also based on the view that developing countries should place appropriate priorities in the allocation of their resources on their own economic and social development. The ODA Charter also states that the regional

priorities of economic assistance will continue to be placed on Asia with which Japan has had close relationship in historical, geographical, political and economic terms.

Former Prime Minister Shinzo Abe and present Prime Minister Takaichi have strongly endorsed “JAPAN IS BACK” to refurbish Japan’s image as an economic and security leader in the Indo-Pacific. As a result of the shifting of power pole with the rapid rise of Chinese economic and military capabilities Japan felt the need to rethink its post-war, US-imposed pacifist constitution. In 2014, Prime Minister Abe’s government reinterpreted Japanese Constitution to theoretically fight overseas and he gave it the tools to do, buying stealth fighters and building Japan’s first aircraft carriers since World War II to accommodate them. “In her first week as prime Minister, Sanae Takaichi announced plans to boost Japanese defense spending by the spring of 2006, accelerating the previous timeline to do so by two years. Japan plans to strengthen their supply chain of critical minerals and rare earths which are essential components of advanced technologies and modern infrastructure as China is unwavering in its mission to unilaterally change the status quo by coercive force.”⁴

Prime Minister Abe’s speech to the Indian Parliament titled “Confluence of Two Seas” and the paper “Asia’s Democratic Security Diamond published by Abe in 2012, hinted at the formation of QUAD and the kind of security arrangement he envisioned for Indo-Pacific.”⁵

The Indo-Pacific and the Quad Prime Minister Abe envisioned has three basic characteristics

- 1) The need for a way of thinking that unites the Pacific and Indian Oceans, which are undergoing remarkable economic development and increasing their influence as centers of world politics. According to him, in the past, when a major war broke out in Europe, this affected the world and was considered a world war. However, if a major war broke out in Asia now, the entire world would be affected. In other words, Asia has also begun to have a level of influence such that it can earn the title of the center of the world.
- 2) According to Prime Minister Abe, the region has been threatened by Chinese domination, evoking the need for a counter-concept. The Indo-Pacific, according to him includes all countries that have territorial problems with China. The Quad is a group that consists of all influential countries in the Indo-Pacific with the exception of China. As such, the Indo-Pacific and the Quad are useful when considering Cooperation among countries as a strategy against China.
- 3) It is a concept that highlights the importance of India. The difference between “Indo-Pacific” and “Asia-Pacific”, a term which is used since the end of Cold war, is India. Within Quad, Japan and

Australia are allies of US, and if it were only about cooperation among these three countries there are already many opportunities, so there is no need for a new framework. The reason for advocating the Quad was to get India into the ranks.

In other words, the combination of the Indo-Pacific and the Quad as envisioned by Prime-Minister Abe was to counter China's domination by considering the rapidly growing region as one and including India. ⁶

India is cautious about joining QUAD grouping as it is primarily focus on military cooperation. India promotes cooperative relations for maritime security and counter terrorism under a Japan-US-Australia-India framework, including the Malabar exercises but in land based and aviation matters, it promotes cooperation on bilateral basis, such as US-India, Japan-India and Australia-India, thus applying different approaches. There is a major difference in perceptions between Japan, the US, Australia and India in the Quad is while the first three countries have no land borders with China, India does. Therefore, China is much more serious matter for India than for Japan, the US, or Australia, and the issue of the India-China border must be handled with caution because it could immediately escalate into fighting. The problem for India is, while the quad is useful for countering China, if the later recognizes it as a military alliance against it and decides to fight, India is likely to be the first to be attacked. From China's viewpoint Japan, the US, and Australia are countries across the sea, while India is a country that is very close to it by land; making it easy to attack. As such, India has a dilemma. Cooperation with Quad countries could initially strengthen the defence of the India-China border. However, cooperation with the Quad should not provoke China too much. Hence while reiterating that India does not consider the Quad as a military alliance against China. In fact, India wants to pursue defence cooperation on bilateral basis only.

Japan-India convergence in Economic sphere

As for the complementarily in economic fields, India is the first country to receive ODA from Japan and today India has become the largest recipient of it. From 2019 to 2020 a massive amount of loan i.e. 6.2 trillion Japanese Yuan has been coming to Indian economy. The money is been primarily utilized in transportation sector especially railways (metro) and rail projects. In the early 1990s when India was facing major financial crisis, and when no other country was willing to offer help India, Japan helped India with its ODA. Since then, the two countries have established a strong economic partnership one after the other. Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe (2015) is of the opinion that Japan-India ties will determine the course of Indo-pacific in the coming decades.

The most important of all is the one signed in 2014, when Japan and India established one of the biggest economic partnerships – “Japan-India Special Strategic and Global Partnership” which aims to double Japan’s FDI in India every five years and double the number of Japanese companies working in India for every five years. The prime ministers of the two countries also agreed to advance shared interests in peace stability and prosperity focusing on areas like civil nuclear energy, defence, high-tech collaboration and regional security. Japan’s involvement in India has both Political and strategic utility. It is a means for Japan to undo its Loss Decade in which Japan has not experienced any economic growth i.e. 1991 to 2022. On the other hand, Japan’s investment to India has a lot of bearing for the future of both the countries. For Japan, in terms of human capital India can offer a lot. Japan’s slow population growth coupled with its aging population is making Japan look out for human capital to help its economic activity going. Japan needs human capital and for fulfilling this need India can be of a great help. On the Indian side Japanese ODA has benefitted both the countries with the help and expertise of Japan’s Quality driven management introduced strong and resilient projects. One of upcoming such projects is the “Mumbai-Ahmadabad Highway Project” which is expected to use Japan’s Shinkansen Technology.

Importance of North East India in Japan-India Relations

Japan considers East and Northeast India as vital conduit between South Asia and Southeast Asia. Being a strategically important region this region can be of immense help in its larger scheme of things regarding securing its national interest. Therefore, development of Eastern India for its ports and the North eastern India for its location astride South Asia and Southeast Asia and the enabling the continental trade between these two subcontinents is in Japan’s must do list.

Being an Island maritime nation Japan’s peace and prosperity depends on the Indo-Pacific Ocean and its sea lanes. Japan imports almost all of its natural resources through these sea routes including strategic resources like gas, oil and majority of the mineral resources it requires to sustain its economy. In 2023, “The Industrial Value Chain Concept connecting Bay of Bengal and Northeast India” was proposed by the former Prime Minister Fumio Kisida. The proposed concept envisions a united East and North East India, Bangladesh and other neighbouring parts of Bay of Bengal region into a whole economic zone with a market of over 300 million people. Therefore “Japan has made efforts to develop this region in terms of not only economic interests but also political, diplomatic and strategic interests. Indeed, the northeastern India serves as a convergence point for India’s Act East Policy and the FIOP policy of Japan. It also believes that as North East India and East India encompassing Bay of Bengal region were once a thriving trading region, the trading potential of the region can be revived if appropriate connectivity is established along the way.

It is for this reason that Japan is making a sincere effort to help in upgrading the potential of this region for a productive trade and commerce. In fact, “Japan possesses practical expertise in infrastructure and economic corridors such as “East West Economic corridor” and the “Southern economic corridor” in the Mekong region. These economic corridors are some of the most successful industrial value chain projects in the world.⁷

As for the development of Infrastructure projects undertaken with the Japanese assistance in the Northeastern India over 22,000 crores in ODA in areas such as roads, water supply and sewage, electricity, healthcare and biodiversity have been sanctioned. Among the various projects, the most important or the flagship project is the “North East Road Network Connectivity Improvement Project”. This project connects Tura-Dalu, Shillong-Dawki, Dhubri-Phulbhari, Kailashahar-Khowai and Khowai-Sarbhoom enhancing connectivity in states of Assam, Meghalaya and Tripura by connecting and upgrading national highways and bridges. At the same time, Japan is improving access on the Bangladesh side through the “Cross Border Road Network Improvement Project”. In order to improve the access a bridge is also being constructed at the Dhaka-Benapole and Baraiyarhat-Ramgarh access.

Japan identifies three sectors as high priority sectors in Northeast India. They are Agriculture, human resources and Semi-conductors in the Northeast Region of India. JICA identifies Bamboo industry and Horticulture sector as having an area of huge potential in the region. However, human resource development is the main focus. Japanese government is of the view that it is utmost essential to cultivate human resources. In order to create a viable and productive value chain, human resources of the region have to be developed because it is the people of the region who has to develop the farmland or start a business or nurture industries, and therefore it is very essential to cultivate the human resources. Building good roads, bridges and railways alone will not make the industrial value chain a successful endeavour. Japan and the North east states of India share a complementary interest in case of human resources. People in these states have high educational qualifications but they struggle to find jobs as there is lack of employment opportunities in this region. Meanwhile, Japan is facing an acute problem of manpower shortage and aging population. It is in this area that the employable youth of the region can get some opportunity to earn a living. Today Japan is accepting Indian workers in fields such as agriculture, construction, caregiving and hospitality for three to five years or longer if conditions are met through the Technical Intern Training Programme (TITP) and Specified Skilled Worker Scheme (SSW). This scheme helps solve some of the problems faced by Japan regarding severe labour shortages and at the same time provide skill development to the people of Northeast India. However, the number of Indian workers, which is about 54,000⁸ only is

very meager compared to its overall population, while there are about 5,18,000 Vietnamese⁹, about 1,69,000 Indonesian¹⁰ and about 2,06,000 Nepali¹¹ workers in Japan as of 2024. Japanese embassy is working towards increasing the number of Indian workers especially from Northeast India by holding job fairs and information sessions for local governments and SMES.

Semiconductors: This is one of the most important components of modern industry. All the industrially developed countries of the world highly depend on semiconductor which is obtained from Rare Earth Elements. At present around 90% of the production of Semi-Conductor or refinement of Rare Earth Elements is done in China. Both India and Japan need to develop the refinement of Rare Earths in order to convert it into usable semiconductor components in the long run if both countries have to diversify their dependence on China for semiconductor. Then again, the semi-conductor industry involves design, manufacturing, assembly and inspection, with various companies for mining clusters. The Tata group announced the establishment of an OSAT (Outsourced Semiconductor Assembly and Test) factory for semiconductor back-end processes in Morigoan, Assam, in addition to Dholera and Sananand in Gujarat. Some Japanese companies have shown interest in participating in the Morigoan semiconductor cluster, if it is realized. "Semiconductor industry is a highly prioritized industry for both India and Japan, and both countries have signed a Japan-India semiconductor Supply Chain Partnership in October 2013.

Other than the above stated economic complementariness, there are also some very pertinent geostrategic reasons as to why Japan is interested in India's Northeastern states.

First, Japan considers China's increase military economic and infrastructural reach in the Indian Ocean and Belt and Road linked projects as a security challenge in the long run. By strengthening ties with India and investing in Northeast India Japan is trying to diversify regional influence and build a network of likeminded partners along China's periphery.

Second, developing connectivity, security cooperation and resilient infrastructure with India strengthens the alignments based on Japan-India bilaterally; Japan-India-ASEAN trilaterally and Australia, India, Japan and New Zealand as Quad.

Third, Improved transport and logistics through northeast India would provide Japan access and basing options in times of need. It also enables Japan to project its soft power and sustain economic ties. This strategy is imperative in order to ensure Japan's strategic maritime balance.

Fourth, the location of Northeast India is very crucial in today's geopolitical scenario. The region lies astride corridors linking South Asia and Southeast Asia. Therefore, Japan is aiding in projects that can create overland routes between northeastern India, Myanmar and ASEAN markets. It would reduce Japanese dependence on maritime routes vulnerable to disruption.

Fifth, for Japan the region offers untapped markets, natural resources, and hydropower and agribusiness opportunities. There is also "scope for light manufacturing logistics, cold chains and agro processing that fit Japan's supply chain needs" and also the Japan+ India+ ASEAN" production network.

Sixth, in order to establish commercially viable routes linking Japan's markets from the landlocked Northeast towards southeast Asia and South Asia, Japan is supporting India's Act East policy and regional corridor projects like trilateral highway connecting India Myanmar and Thailand and the Kaladan Multi-Modal transit Project.

Seventh, East and Northeast East India provides Japanese companies projects where it can finance and manage large infrastructure projects via institutions like JBIC, JICA and another private contractor. Rail, electrification, metro-system and port modernization are some of the prospective sectors here.

Eighth, Japanese companies invest in power transmission rural electrification and grid resilience to support industrialization and to reduce fossil fuel dependence in the region. This region is also highly conducive for hydropower and renewable projects.

Ninth, in order to raise invertibility, Japan also funds technical assistance, skill development, vocational training and urban planning in the region.

Tenth, Japan is of the opinion that by deepening engagement with the NER which is a strategically sensitive region infested with long drawn history of insurgency related issues, can help reduce regional instability by helping in facilitating better connectivity, jobs and state capacity. In the process strengthen Japan India relation also.

Conclusion

We have dealt with the prospects of Japan India relation in the present uncertain geopolitics of Indo Pacific with special focus on Northeastern states of India. However, one of the constraints in the successful implementation of the Japan-India endeavour is Political instability in Myanmar is a cause of concern for both Japan and India as both the countries have high stakes in a peaceful and stable Myanmar. Myanmar

has a fair share of important sea Lanes of commerce on the one hand and on the other hand the economic arteries joining India and the heart of ASEAN, starts from Myanmar. So, unless Myanmar becomes stable Japan and India's continental route to ASEAN will fail and so does the vision of economic empowerment of Northeast India states through India's Act East policy will be hard to realize.

Japan India relations are destined to be the most important partnership in the present geostrategic scenario in the world where American economic hegemony is on the wane and China is all set to overtake as the most powerful country in economic as well as military sphere. Japan-India partnership holds a lot of positive prospects for Northeast Indian states as Japan is taking a major role in enhancing connectivity for the region. The government of India as well as the respective state governments in particular should take all the resources in hand to make the best out of Japan's outreach. Human resource development is an area where most special effort should be put. Time has come for all the people in the northeast to collectively work together for a better future ahead. For this to happen the people of these states to have come above ethnic and other divisive lines which hinders the smooth conduct of business.

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